

**AN EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAPE COAST COLLEGE OF
DISTANCE EDUCATION CLOTHING AND TEXTILES
CURRICULUM IN THE MIDDLE ZONE (ASHANTI &
BRONG AHAFO REGIONS) OF GHANA**

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Abstract:

The study evaluated the implementation of clothing and textiles curriculum in the middle zone of Distance Education trainees of university of cape coast in Ghana. The objectives were to examine the teaching methods used by facilitators, investigate the mastery and competency level of trainees, elicit respondents' suggestions to improve on the implementation of the clothing and textiles curriculum. The goal-oriented method was used. Trainees who were in their final year and their facilitators of eight study centers in the middle zone (Ashanti and Bono Regions). The purposive sampling technique was used to select 210 trainees and 8 facilitators for the study. Questionnaires and interviews were administered to collect data. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentages. The results revealed that 50.4% of facilitators had worked between 6 and 10 years and most of them (87.5%) were senior tutors but lack in-service training. Only 12% of trainees had interest in clothing and textiles and 79% did not do vocational studies at diploma level. The least used methods of teaching were computer assisted instructions and practical work, and real objects and pictures were used. There is non-availability of laboratories and resources for practical work. About half (50%) of trainees were competent and had average to low level of comprehension of subject matter. For improvement, there is the need to provide laboratories and resources in the study centers for learning, facilitators change their methods of teaching to include practical work and CAI and radio/video recordings for trainees to access learning, sketches and assessment items in modules made learner centered or friendly. Other suggestions were sufficient time to complete the units in the modules and a shift from traditional to a blended or hybrid where online is blended with face to face and from

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exam based assessment to a more learner centered approach performance based assessment.

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1. Introduction

Vocational education is the umbrella under which includes all education and preparation for occupation, profession and careers in the sphere of work (Brandon 1970). To ensure quality standards and relevance in skill training, resources in the industry should be available and used in the classrooms and workshops for skill acquisition and training. The prime objective of clothing and textile curriculum is to provide knowledge and requisition of skills in a manner that will best meet the needs of trade as well as teaching and learning. An important time that correct practices are learnt is during teaching and learning. At that time, a learner is exposed to resources for skill acquisition.

Distance Education is a form of education in which students and teachers are separate physically during instructions most of the time and uses various technologies to student teacher communication. It focuses on traditional and non-traditional students who are full-time, non-residents or people in remote areas. This expands access to education and training to general populace and business because of schedules that are flexible. The college of Distance Education (CODE) was established in 1997 and upgraded to College status in 2014. The College runs both Education Studies and Business Studies. The objectives of CODE include providing opportunities for people to pursue high education and train more professional teachers for all levels of education in Ghana Education Service.

CODE aimed at providing opportunities for applicants who qualify for admission but fail to enter the conventional university system due to some constraints. Currently CODE has 69 learning centers and print based delivery mode across all regions in Ghana. The programmes rolled out ensure that there is no disparity in teaching and learning and assessment between the conventional system and distance learning system. The same lecturers in the conventional system write modules for distance learning, set questions for quizzes, examinations and grade students finally. The quizzes and examinations for distance students are based on the modules they use.

College of Distance Education provide students with modules for all vocational studies courses. Trainees study all modules on their own and attend face to face lecture at various study centers bi-weekly. All trainees study management in living, foods and nutrition and clothing and textiles as vocational studies courses for two-year post-diploma education students. The clothing and textiles modules help trainees among others to acquire insight, knowledge and skills in:

- pattern making basics and alteration,

- good grooming and clothing management,
- pattern adaptation and the supplies needed,
- body measurement and processes in clothing construction,
- textiles and fabric production, their properties and uses,
- manipulating darts to come up with different designs of bodices and skirts,
- pattern making for different designs or styles fabric preparation, cutting out, transferring pattern markings,
- methods of clothing construction,
- differentiating between underlying fabrics,
- outlining steps to be taken to care and maintain clothes,
- exposure of how the clothing industry operates.

Since the inception of vocational studies by College of Distance Education (UCC) practical aspects of its curriculum has been in crisis since the study centers lack practical rooms and other resources. There are a lot of job opportunities in this area of education and training that these teachers will impart to Junior High School (JHS) and Senior High School (SHS) youth; it is therefore very important for them to be skilled in certain areas of the clothing and textiles subject matter for industry.

Graduates from CODE(UCC) are expected to possess these skills so that they as teachers can impart them to the young ones they teach and be able to set up their businesses. It is envisaged that vocational studies (Clothing and Textiles) is well implemented. How these knowledge and skill training is imparted is something to investigate. The implementation of curriculum refers to what happens in practice as compared to what is supposed to happen. The current clothing and textiles curriculum and modules for vocational studies is not known to have gone through any revision aimed at improving it to enrich the skills. It is fundamental or imperative for distance education institutions to design and deliver high quality instructional modules for their programs of study with standards by monitoring and improving the modules. SAIDE (2003) suggest that the appropriate standard was by periodically reviewing the modules in line with current trends and the feedback obtained from students. Posner (1995)) says the main reason to conduct an evaluation of any kind in a curriculum is to provide information for decision making about that curriculum. This study was conducted to find out how the clothing and textiles curriculum is being implemented in the study centers; that is CODE (UCC) Ashanti and Bono Regions (Middle Zone) to increase relevance to skill training and employment.

2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the Implementation of Clothing and textiles curriculum in the middle zone (Ashanti and Bono Regions). Specifically, to;

- 1) look at background of facilitators and students,

- 2) examine the teaching methods used by facilitators to impart knowledge and skills to students,
- 3) investigate the facilities and resources available for clothing and textiles,
- 4) find out trainees level of comprehension of the subject matter taught,
- 5) elicit the challenges of teaching and learning clothing and textiles at the study centres and gather suggestion to improve implementation.

2.1 Research Questions

In line with the objectives of the study, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

- 1) What is the background information of trainees of Vocational Studies?
- 2) Which teaching methods were used to facilitate Clothing and Textiles trainees?
- 3) What resources and facilities were available at the study centres for skill development?
- 4) What is the level of comprehension and competence of trainees in clothing and textiles subject matter?
- 5) In what ways can the limitations to the implementation of clothing and textiles for UCC- CODE trainees be overcome in the study centres?

2.2 Significance of the Study

The study is of great benefit to students and facilitators of vocational studies (Clothing and Textiles) on CODE-UCC program. Students will acquire requisite skills, needed as teacher trainees to be better equipped in their job. Facilitators would have evidence to support their requisition for teaching and learning resources for their courses. The finding again would help curriculum planners and policy makers to improve Vocational Studies modules to address problems with topics and skills they need to acquire.

2.3 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study was an evaluation of the implementation of the clothing and textile curriculum. The goal-oriented model of evaluation used involves identifying, clarifying and stating the purpose of an educational activity and then addressing the context to which objectives have been achieved or is being achieved. The study covered eight (8) study centres in the middle zone, 4 from Ashanti Region and 4 from Bono Region.

3. Review of Related Literature

With regards to improvement in academic and professional performance, curriculum evaluation cannot be played down. Literature was reviewed to cover the following: purpose of distance education in Ghana, curriculum implementation and curriculum evaluation, methods or strategies for teaching, instruction and assessment of Clothing and Textiles curriculum, instructional resources and facilities for clothing and textile,

Clothing and textile facilitators and trainees as well as limitations to the teaching and learning of clothing and textiles in Distance study centers.

3.1 Purpose of Distance Education

Vocational education is the umbrella under which includes all education and preparation for occupation, professions and careers in sphere of work. Avoke et al., (1998) said that vocational education involves all activities and experiences that are directed towards making that recipient functional and acquire job related skills. One of the aims of Technical Vocational Education and Training in Ghana is to identify and train vocational education teachers (TVET Policy, 2004). One of the terms of reference for 2002 education review committee was on the constrained access to different levels of educational ladder, ICT and Distance education, to this government of the day accepted their recommendation to increase and expand support for distance Education. Tertiary institutions expanding their operation to include distance education programs and to cover subject in the school curriculum (Ministry of Education Youth and Sports, 2004).

3.2 Curriculum Implementation and Evaluation

A curriculum implementation according to Adentwi (2005) is the process of translating curriculum plans into practical teaching learning in the classroom throughout the entire school system. It is an attempt to alter individuals' knowledge, actions and attitudes. He added that, many people are skeptical about curriculum implementation because experience has shown that many theoretically sound ideas materials, programme policies and activities and activities that are introduced in the school system never really get implementation in the classroom situation. This observation and thinking about curriculum implementation have led to investigation into factors that impede or enhance the implementations process of a curriculum.

They are many and varied in given situation. Curriculum evaluation is a systematic process of determining whether the curriculum as designed and implemented has produced or is producing the intended and desired results. Adentwi (2005) defines curriculum evaluation as the collection and use of information as a basis for decision about an educational program. Aboagye (2003) added that the purpose of curriculum evaluation is to see whether curriculum objectives are achieved or being achieved so that changes in them can be made if necessary. The curriculum evaluation models are different conceptions about evaluation and how it should be carried. In this study, the goal-oriented model was used. This model makes it necessary for programme developer to clarify the relationship between specific activities or services that are offered and particular results or outcomes that are to be achieved. Hammond (2005) stated that it requires paying attention to the logical steps to the desired outcome.

3.3 Methods / Strategies for Teaching Clothing and Textiles

Attention must be given to the way in which resources interact with the receiver. The skills needed to perform certain roles do not come naturally but have to be taught and acquired through learning. Gavor et al (2006) explained that teaching facilitates learning. It is an attempt to help someone acquire or change some skills attitude etc. and the goal is to bring about desired learning in students. Talabi (2001) listed some teaching strategies as demonstration, project lecture, laboratory work, programmed instruction with Amoah and Amissah (2001) adding integration team teaching and computer assisted instruction (CAI). The choice of strategies depends to a large extent on what is hoped to be achieved, the level of learners and the nature of lesson. They added that we need to diversity our teaching strategies to meet the rapidly changing trends in development in the world today. Teaching clothing and Textiles as a course allows learners to acquire knowledge and skills at their homes and study centers in such a way that they will be interested with facilitators support. Arubayi (2004) pointed out that clothing and textiles has six central themes: study of fabrics garment construction, clothing maintenance, consumer education, decorative process and wardrobe planning these themes have several subject matter or topic under them in the clothing and textiles curriculum for teacher trainees. Teachers need among other things a curriculum and assessment system that facilitates rather than thwarts. Students true academic potential and ongoing learning and professional development in a best innovative practice throughout their entire teaching career. Loucks-Horsley et al (2003) explains that professional development programs should address content instruction, pedagogy content knowledge, knowledge of learning development and efficacy if good teaching will be fostered. Moan, Leach and Stevens (2005) says that distance education model must be grounded in a specific set of learning objectives; increasing teachers' knowledge in a domain, helping teachers master content-specific pedagogical approaches or developing practical skills. Distance education programs can help trainee teachers reach their destination by designing high quality experience with practices and assessment selecting appropriate technologies as SAIDE (2007) asserts that poorly designed technology courses and confound learning frustrates learners and instructors and results in high attrition rates. Burns (2011) asserts that *"an instructional approach alone is no guarantee of quality instruction. It is only part of the recipe"*. If students are to learn in a distance medium and emerge as qualified teachers, distance institutions must model high quality teaching skills. Libero (2004) said *"in distance education where the paradigm must be learner centered, the instructional materials and modules play significant roles. you must have high quality instructional materials if you want to maintain high quality instructions and academic standards. Instructional materials and modules can and are prepared according to strict standards, while the quality of live lectures of different professors can vary considerably."*

Multi-media-based distance learning combines a number of content formats; text, audio, full motion video, still image animation, computer-aided instructions, etc. (Burns 2011). Gardener (1983) supported by Mayers (2001) added that multimedia has two

potential benefits; that a combination of text and images simultaneously helps both teachers and students learn effectively by aiding learner's memory and address individual learning styles and their frames of knowing. Sloan (2008) classified as traditional, where content is delivered in written, oral or audiovisual format, web facilitated where, where web-technology is used to facilitate what is essentially a face to face setting, Blended/Hybrid, where online is blended with face to face meetings and online where course delivers vast bulk of content online with typically no face to face meetings. Marzano (2000) opined that realigning within a distance learning system will require shifting from traditional exam-based assessment in which discrete facts are measured to a more learner centered approach of projects, portfolios and performance-based assessment of what, how and why students have learned.

3.4 Instructional Resources and Facilities of Clothing and Textiles

Instructional materials are prepared and used by facilitators and students to make content easier to understand and more interesting. Talabi (2001) defined instructional media to include a wide range of materials and devices designed to provide realistic imagery and substitutes experience to enrich curricular experiences. He added that those widely applied to teaching in the classroom include bulletin boards, pictures, textbooks specimen, computer open and close circuit television, laboratories, workshop etc. Also satellites capable of transmitting more than one hundred televisions educational programs included. He explained that students can sit at home, hostel, classroom etc. and tune into a wide variety educational broadcast. All subjects in the school curriculum including clothing and textiles find wide application in these instructional media. This means that the teacher or facilitator of today is faced with new challenge in his or her task of imparting knowledge. If the teachers continue to use verbal and printed programs alone for accomplishing his or her teaching commitment, he or she will fail to achieve his or her objectives and learners will find classroom work boring and unmoving and will take a heavy toll on the nations manpower resources. Gavor et al., (2006) posit that instructional materials are intended to aid learning readily so should be chosen to illustrate lesson content, whether it is applicable to use for the particular situation so that objectives of the lesson would be achieved, learners will be involved to make lesson learner centered.

3.5 Clothing and Textiles Facilitators & Trainees

The teacher is said to be the key to the entire instructional program. It is believed that the teacher's behavior in the classroom m determines whether or not schools meet the challenges of life (Gavor et al., 2006). According to them, a teacher and for that matter a clothing and textiles teacher should know his or her subject matter, above the level of the learners and is abreast with time or current knowing the development in the field. They added that a good teacher knows how to deliver lessons with the various teaching strategies and uses them effectively.

Students are at the central points in curriculum implementation process. They hold the what is actually transmitted and adopted from the curriculum. Arkhurst (2004) asserts that clothing and textiles students with anxiety problems will not be able to acquire the skills needed. A student's participation in class helps in the acquisition of skills in clothing and textiles. She added that learner's attitude to the subject may hinder or motivate learning of skills as some learners perceive clothing and textiles as difficult and time consuming. Sifuna et al (2010) points out that quality is at the heart of all education systems and the quest to ensure that learners achieve decent learning outcomes and acquire values and skills to help them play positive role in their society. Amoah and Amisah (2001) listed in addition to the above points that good teachers should cover adequately the prescribed syllabus, include and use appropriate teaching resources, illustrate the practical implication of the theory and link materials to laboratory or practical work. Benneh (2006) and Adegoke (2003) indicates that the mission of Ghana's teacher education is to provide a comprehensive teacher education program through pre-service and in-service training that would produce competent, committed and dedicated teachers to improve the quality of the teaching and learning. To Asare (2010) the real threat to learning is how teaching is done and suggested that teachers must be taught to engage learners in such a way that the learners own and make sense of activities to promote learning.

4. Methodology

The goal-oriented evaluation design was used for the study. It involves identifying, clarifying and stating the purpose of an educational activity and then assessing the extent to which the purpose has been or are being achieved. According to Adentwi (2005) the goal-oriented evaluation uses program specific goal and objective as the criteria for determining success. Worthen and Sanders (1987) said information gained from this design could be used to formulate the purpose of the activity, the assessment procedures and devices used to determine the achievement purposes.

The study was carried out in the middle zone (Ashanti and Bono Regions) of the CODE administrative grouping. The focus was on Distance Education made up of twenty-two (22) study centres in the region. The Zone is made up of Diploma and degree students in business and education programs. The study was conducted in Ashanti and Bono Regions because the researcher facilitates vocational studies in one of the study centres and have observed that the curriculum has not been evaluated within the last ten years. It means no evaluation has been introduced to match the current technological advancement of the clothing and textile industry to attract youth to pursue the course and to improve on the curriculum if there is the need.

The Post-Diploma trainees and their facilitators numbering two hundred and eighteen were used for the study in the eight study centre in the middle zone. The choice of the study centre was selected by purposive sampling technique. The reason being that

the students who were going through the program were the right students and can provide the needed information for the study. The facilitators were sampled because they were the people who were implementing the curriculum for the program in the study area. Structured questionnaires and interview guides were generated to collect the necessary data from the respondents.

5. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Facilitators background information (N= 8)

Characteristics	Option	Frequency	Percentage
Work Experience	1 – 5	1	12.5%
	6 – 10	5	50%
	Above 10	2	24.5%
Rank	Senior Tutor	7	87.5%
	Tutor	1	12.5%
In Service Training	Yes	1	12.5%
	No	7	87.5%

Source: Field survey, 2019.

From table 1 50% of facilitators had worked between 6 to 10 years and 24.5% had worked above 10 years. Only 12.5% had worked for 1 to 5 years. Most of the facilitators (87.5%) were senior tutors and only 12.5% was a tutor. The results show that majority were experience in the teaching profession and were qualified as well. However, 85.5% responded no to in-service training. No matter how experienced and well qualified facilitators are before appointment, there is the need for in-service training with time to augment Adegoke (2003) and Benneh (2006) assertion that in-service training which is scarcely done: takes place to produce competent, committed and dedicated teachers to improve the quality of teaching and learning.

Trainees who offered vocational studies at diploma level were only 45(21%) and rest 165(79%) did not offer vocational studies. All respondents were enthusiastic in studying vocational studies by distance, but some had interest in some particular courses. Only 12% were interested in clothing and textiles and 47% and 41% were interested in management in living and food and nutrition, respectively. Those who did not like clothing and textiles explained that they accepted it because clothing and textiles was part of the available program for vocational studies. Trainees interest matters in training and therefore where it is very low, attitude to subject may hinder learning skills. This is supported by Arkhurst (2004) that clothing and textiles student with anxiety problems will not be able to acquire skills needed. This will affect quality as Sifuna et al (2010) points out that quality is at the heart of all education system and the quest to ensure that learners achieve decent learning outcomes and acquire values and skills to help them play positive roles in their society.

Figure 1: Vocational courses studied by trainees at diploma level and interest in vocational courses at post diploma level (n=210)

Source: Field Survey 2019.

Table 3: Facilitators responses on methods of teaching and types of resources of used to teach at the study centers (n=8)

Characteristics	Options	Frequency		
		Often	Sometimes	Never
Methods of teaching	Lecture	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	
	Discussion	8 (100%)		
	Demonstration	7 (87.5%)	1 (12.5%)	
	Practicals		6 (75%)	2 (25%)
	Computer Assisted Instructions			8 (100%)
Types of resources	Real Objects	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	
	Pictures/Drawings	8 (100%)		
	Videos/Recordings			8 (100%)
	Internet application			8 (100%)

Source: Field Survey 2019.

From Table 3, the most popular teaching method with 100% was discussion followed by demonstration (87.5%) and lecture (75%). The least method used was computer assisted instructions followed by practicals or laboratory work (25%). This means that clothing and textiles which has a lot of content on skill acquisition for trainees lacks the exposure that they should get as part of pre- service training necessary for job at the study centers selected which may lead to poor preparation of trainees. Darling- Hammond (2006)

asserts one of the significant indicators of trainees' success is an excellent teacher; one who facilitates learning in the classroom. If distance education program leaves clothing and textiles trainees poorly prepared, there will be increased inefficiency. There is the need for distance trainees to exhibit these skills as Burns (2011) asserts that *"an instructional approach alone is no guarantee of quality instructions: it is only part of the recipe. If students are to learn in a distance medium and emerge as qualified teachers distance instructions must model high quality teaching skills."*

Table 4: Resource available at the study centers by respondents (n=210)

Facilities / Resources	Available		Not Available	
	Teachers	Students	Teachers	Students
Laboratory	2 (25%)	42 (20%)	6 (75%)	168 (80%)
Measuring tools (tape measure)	8 (100%)	20 (4.8%)	--	190 (90.4%)
Marking tools (tailors chalk)	8 (100%)	26 (12%)	--	184 (87.6%)
Cutting tools (shears scissor)	8 (100%)	101 (48%)	--	109 (52%)
Patterns pieces and slopers	5 (65.5%)	--	3 (37.5%)	210 (100%)
Cello tape, pins, thumb tacks	8 (100%)	29 (14%)	--	179 (86%)
Closures (Buttons, hook & eye)	8 (100%)	--	--	210 (100%)
Underlying fabrics(Vilene)	4 (50%)	--	4 (50%)	210 (100%)
Detergents/ Soaps	6 (75%)	8 (3.8%)	2 (25%)	202 (96%)
Bleaches	4 (5%)	6 (2.8%)	4 (50%)	204 (97%)
Softeners	1 (12.5%)	--	7 (87.5%)	210 (100%)
Starches	1 (12.5%)	--	7 (87.5%)	210 (100%)

Source: Field survey, 2019.

The study investigated the availability of clothing and textile laboratory in study centres. The responses provided by the trainees (80%) and facilitators (75%) indicated that laboratories were not available in the study centers. The clothing and textiles laboratory is one of the facilities needed by facilitators and trainees in the implementation of the curriculum. *"The laboratory is used for helping students to acquire understanding and practical application of cognitive and psychomotor skills"* (Talabi 2001). The laboratory provides the ideal setting for skill development, discovery learning inquiry and problem solving: it is clear that on the average, distance study centre offering clothing and textiles did not have laboratories which is a major setback in the implementation of the clothing and textiles

curriculum. Trainees and facilitators responses show that six out of eleven listed groups of teaching/learning resources were available to teachers or facilitators. Measuring tools, marking tools, cutting tools, cello tape, closures, were at available since 100% agreed to their availability, softeners and starches had 12.5% each agreeing to their availability. Facilitators explained that they were their personal materials they used for demonstrations during face-to-face at the student centre. Majority of trainees indicated the unavailability of resources, thus measuring tools (90.4%), marking tools (87.6%), cutting tools (52%), patterns pieces & slopes (100%), closures (100%), bleaches (97%) and softeners and starches (100%). Unavailability of resources is an indication that trainees will not be able to practice what facilitators demonstrate. Being a practical subject, clothing and textiles trainees need to observe demonstration and practice to develop skills and interest in the job. Theory alone makes lessons boring and difficult to understand. Gavor et al (2006) and Kowalski (2012) agree that availability of teaching learning materials/resources are important factors in the teaching learning process so the objectives of the lesson will be achieved, learners or trainees will be involved to make lesson learner centered. Availability of teaching learning resources was found to be very weak and militates against the implementation of the clothing and textiles curriculum at the study centers.

Table 5: Trainees level of comprehension of clothing & textiles subject matter taught (n=210)

Major Units of Subject Matter	High Freq.	Average Freq.	Low Freq.
Sewing equipment & supplies	160 (77%)	45 (21%)	5 (2%)
Textiles -- from fiber to fabric	30 (14%)	38 (18%)	142 (68%)
Pattern making basics	18 (8.5%)	32 (15%)	160 (76%)
Pattern alterations	29 (14%)	32 (15%)	149 (71%)
Clothing management	124 (59%)	70 (33%)	16 (7.6%)
Clothing construction I	80 (38%)	62 (30%)	68 (32%)
Pattern adaptation I	42 (20%)	24 (11%)	144 (69%)
Pattern adaptation II	31 (15%)	71 (34%)	108 (51%)
The garment production industry	106 (50%)	95 (45%)	10 (4.7%)
Clothing construction II	80 (38%)	108 (51%)	22 (10%)
Clothing maintenance	102 (49%)	103 (49%)	5 (2%)
Managing a clothing industry	92 (43%)	97 (46%)	21 (5.7%)

Figure 2: Competency of Trainees (n=210)

From the Figure 2, about half of respondents (50%) were competent as teacher trainees to deliver the clothing and textiles subject matter. The rest were either not sure (20%) or incompetent (30%). Even though half of the trainees responded in the affirmative, the rest who were not competent or sure creates a worrying impression that they are not capable of imparting knowledge and skills after training. The incompetency emanating from the fact that trainees' level of comprehension of subject matter was low for majority of the listed subject matter. From Table 5 trainees' responses of their level of comprehension of twelve clothing and textiles subject matter. Two topics with the highest level of comprehension was sewing equipment and supplies (77%) followed by clothing management (59%). The content with lower level of comprehension was pattern making basics (76%) followed by pattern alteration (71%), pattern adaptation (69%) and textile fibers to fabrics (68%). Topics that had average comprehension was managing a clothing industry (46%) followed by garment production industry (45%). This is an indication that trainees learning clothing and textiles by distance have sub-standard or poor understanding which will negatively affect quality of curriculum implementation. Sifuna et al (2010) asserts that quality is the heart of all education systems and the quest to ensure that students achieve decent learning outcomes and acquire values and skills that help them play positive roles in their societies. Adegoke (2003) and Benneh (2006) supports that the mission of Ghana Teacher education is to provide a comprehensive teacher education programme through pre-service and in-service training that will produce competent committed and dedicated teachers to improve quality of teaching and learning. Trainees level of comprehension is low so will find it difficult to impart knowledge and skills as required on the teaching field in line with Farrant (2004) statement "*an ignorant teacher cannot enlighten students.*"

Table 6: Trainees responses on challenges militating
 against clothing and textiles curriculum (n=210)

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
No Practical work and assessment	200	95%
Modules have some pictures and diagrams not clear to follow	195	93%
Some self-assessment questions in modules lack answers	195	93%
Time allocation insufficient	180	86%
Incomplete sessions of units during face to face at study centers	180	86%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

From Table 6 it can be ascertained that 95% of respondents listed the absence of practical work and practical assessment as a challenge. This could be as a result of unavailability of laboratories and teaching learning resources in the study centre and has led instructions and assessment for clothing and textiles being only quizzes and examination instead of projects and portfolios which measures performance on how trainees have learnt. On modules for clothing and textiles 93% stated that the pictures and diagrams were not clear to follow and some of the self-assessment questions lack matching answers making it unfriendly to trainees who do not have other sources of information to aid understanding of the content.

Other challenges militating against the implementation of the clothing and textile curriculum were insufficient time allocation and incomplete session of units during face to face at the study centres which go hand in hand. These might emanate from the fact that trainees do not read their modules before attending face to face tutorials at the study centres.

These challenges do not auger well for distance trainees offering clothing and textiles for the program objectives to be achieved as Moon, Leach and Stevens (2005) says that distance education must be grounded in specific set of learning objectives; increasing teachers' knowledge in a particular domain, helping teachers master content specific pedagogical approaches or developing practical skills. This is not the case of trainees in the selected study centers SAIDE (2007) explained that such poorly design courses frustrate and leads to high attrition rates.

6. Suggestions for Improving Clothing and Textiles Curriculum for Distance Learners

- The trainees suggested that laboratories should be provided at the study centres together with teaching/learning material by the university for practical lessons to widen trainees' access to skill acquisition. This will allow trainees to be assessed performing a task in psychomotor domain as Marzano (2000) opined that realigning assessment within a distance learning system will require shifting from traditional exams based assessment in which discrete facts are measured to a more learner centered approach of projects portfolios and performance based assessment that measures what, how and why students have learned.

- Improvement of diagrams and pictures in the modules and provision of answers to the self-assessment questions was suggested by trainees. It is imperative to ensure highest quality delivery as articulated by Libero (2004) “in distance education where the paradigm must be learner centered the instructional materials and modules play significant role. You must have high instructional materials to maintain high quality instructions and academic standards. Instructional materials and module can and are prepared according to strict standards, while the quality of live lectures of professors can vary considerably.” This is in conformity with Wood et al (2004) argument that a key factor in distance learning is to ensure that the course meet the needs of the consumer by increasing the quality of instructional materials.
- Time allocation for practical work and face to face tutorials was proposed by both facilitators and trainees.
- Some respondents suggested exposure of trainees to virtual learning in addition to face- to- face in line with Burns (2011) asserts that print is the primary source of instruction, but support is provided through other means like audio instructions, telephone conversations, “televisual” computer aided instructions web-based learning etc.
- Facilitators should expose trainees to more demonstration and practicals.

7. Summary of Major Findings

Findings arrived at in this study were:

- 1) Even though facilitators implementing the clothing and textiles curriculum in the selected study centers were qualified, experienced, (87.5%) they lack in service training, (85.5%). They use real objects, (75%), picture drawings, (100%), discussion, (100%), demonstration, (87.5%) to teach at the study centers. Resources available for teaching like measuring tools (100%), cutting tools, (100%), closures, (100%), were available for demonstration and teaching, but 75% indicated there were no laboratories which is a setback in the implementation of clothing and textiles curriculum.
- 2) Trainees offering clothing and textiles at post-diploma level in their selected study centers did not study vocational studies at diploma level, (79%), and only 12% were interested in clothing and textiles. They were offering it because it was available as part of the programme.
- 3) The level of comprehension of trainees offering clothing and textiles in the middle zone of CODE-UCC was averagely low. Only two of the listed contents had high level of comprehension. As many as 50% of trainees were not competent or not sure in teaching clothing and textiles.
- 4) Major challenges or limitations listed by trainees are poor unclear sketches and pictures in clothing and textiles modules as well as incomplete unmatched write

up for some photos. Lack of answers to some of the self-assessment questions in the modules. Some facilitators do not complete units during face to face because of insufficient time allocation. No practicals after demonstration.

- 5) Both trainees and facilitators suggested that practical laboratories as well as resources for teaching and learning should be provided by the university to widen trainees access to skill acquisition as it is done for regular students. Review of modules to improve photo/ picture or sketches quality and provide answers to all self-assessment questions. They also suggested that soft copies of demonstrations in the modules should be provided as a sort of hybrid or blended for home learning instead of only face to face at study centers.
- 6) Facilitators also suggested that only those who offered vocational studies at diploma level should be allowed to offer it at the post-diploma level for continuity and interest.

8. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study these insights have been provided into facilitators and trainees experiences on the programme and suggestions provided for improvement.

- 1) Clothing and textiles modules have poorly presented diagrams, photos and answers to self-assessment questions. Some are not self-directing for learning at home.
- 2) Teaching learning resources and practical laboratories were lacking in study centers which have negative effects on the implementation of clothing and textiles curriculum. Practical lessons and computer assisted instruction which draws attention to detail and how knowledge obtained can be applied to their job were also lacking or omitted entirely from methods used by facilitators; a setback in implementation of clothing and textiles curriculum.
- 3) On competency of trainees offering clothing and textiles, it was average and their comprehension level of subject matter was also below expectation.
- 4) Majority of trainees for post diploma did not offer vocational studies at diploma level.
- 5) Facilitators implementing the clothing and textiles on the program lacked in-service training

9. Recommendations

Owing to findings and conclusions made, the following are advocated to be undertaken to improve the implementation of clothing and textiles curriculum of UCC- CODE.

- 1) CODE facilitators for clothing and textiles must be given in-service training to be abreast with current pedagogical strategies, evaluation during face to face tutorial

- to check comprehension of content taught and motivational skills to boost trainees interest and competency levels.
- 2) For a practical course like clothing and textiles, study centers should be provided with laboratories and teaching learning resources.
 - 3) The university through CODE and facilitators for clothing and textiles should consider a blended or hybrid mode of delivery as a sort of multi-media based distance learning.
 - 4) Review clothing and textiles modules is necessary to make them more learner friendly. In addition, audiovisual processes of some parts should be available at some sites on the internet for trainees to visit, download and practice on their own together with the books to improve comprehension.
 - 5) Facilitators should be given periodic in-service training

References

- Aboagye, J. K. (2003). *Some Issues in Curriculum Development* (3rd ed), Accra: City Publishers.
- Adegoke, K. A. (2003). *Capacity Building of Lead teacher training institutions in sub-Saharan Africa*. UNESCO. Retrieved from www.unesco.org, on 10/01/2020.
- Adentwi, K. I. (2005). *Curriculum Development: An introduction*. Kumasi: Wilas Press Limited.
- Alkin, M. C. and Owen, J. M. (2006). *Programme Evaluation: Forms and Approaches*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Amissah, P. A. K. and Amoah, S. A., (2001). *Notes on Teacher Education: Principles and Practice*; Unpublished Lecture Notes.
- Arubayi, D. (2004). *A case study of Teaching Area Preference of Home Economics part time*. Abraka, Nigeria; Unpublished B. Ed Thesis Delta State University.
- Asare, K. B. (2010). Teachers' receptivity to curriculum innovations. *Ontario Journal of African Educational Research*, 1(4), 81-94.
- Avoke, M., Hayford, S. K., Ihenacho, J., and Ocloo, M. A (1998). *Issues in special education*. Accra: City Printers.
- Benneh, M. (2006). *Particular Issues in Teacher Education and Training in Ghana*. Dakar Senegal: UNESCO (TTISSA).
- Burns, M. (2011). *Distance Education for teacher training; modes, models and methods*. Washington: Education development center.
- Farrant, J. S. (2004). *Principles and Practice of Education*. England: Longman Group Ltd.
- Gardner, H. (1983). In *Frames of mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligence*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gavor, M., Ampong I., Kwakye F., and Offie –Ansah, C. (2006) *Vocational Studies III: Methods of Teaching Vocational Studies*. Cape Coast: University Press.

- Hammond D. L. (2005) *A good Teacher in Every Classroom: Preparing the highly qualified our children deserve*. San Francisco; Jossey-Bass.
- Libero, F. (2004). *Distance education in UP: Options and directions*. Paper produced for the university of the Philippines Open University. Los Banos: UP Open University. Retrieved 12 January 2005, from <http://www.UPOU.org/book/options.htm>.
- Marzano, R. J. (2000). *Transforming classroom grading*. Alexandria, NA: Association of supervision and curriculum development.
- Mayer, R. (2001). *Multimedia learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports. (2004). White paper on the report of the education reform review committee. Ghana Government.
- Moon, B., Leach, J. and Stevens, M.P.(2005). *Designing open and distance learning for teacher education in Sub-Saharan Africa: A tool kit for educators and planners (PDF document)*. Washington DC: World bank retrieved from <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/EXTRAFREGTOPDISED/Resources/Teacher-education Toolkit> on May13, 2020.
- Sifuna, D., N., and Sawamura, N. (2010) *Challenges of quality education in sub-Saharan African countries*. New York: Nova Science Publishers.
- Sloan, C. (2008). *Staying the course: Online education in the United States*. Wellesley MA: Babson college. South African Institute of Education (SAIDE), (2003). Minimum targets for distance education in South Africa-2003. Unpublished paper, (Johannesburg: SAIDE).
- Talabi, J. K. (2001). *Educational Technology: Methods, Tools and Techniques*. Lagos: universal Press.
- Wood, D. G., Roberts-Becker, M., Osborne, R., Van Nostrand, J., Winn, S. A., & Ziehr, C. (2004). Total quality management strategic plan for distance course development. Retrieved February 15, 2020.

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DISTANCE EDUCATION CLOTHING AND TEXTILES CURRICULUM IN THE MIDDLE ZONE
(ASHANTI & BRONG AHAFO REGIONS) OF GHANA

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